

WORKSHOP 3: MONITORING AND INDICATORS

Date: 02.03.2024

Duration: 1,5 hours

Number of participants: 5 people

Profile of participants: Young people 22-27 years old, residing in Germany (Thuringia or Saxony-Anhalt) coming from EU and non-EU countries

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Workshop Report

The third workshop was combined with the second one, taking place on the same date with the same members of the Learning Community. Since the interventions were already selected for the Leverage Points exercise, the participants started with brainstorming the indicators of change.

The Learning Community followed the steps proposed in the methodology guide, developing indicators for detecting and monitoring change, as a response to selected interventions. The discussion included consideration for the overall impact stemming from a pack of interventions, that should lead to a transformative change.

1. Night Hike

by connecting personally to biodiversity, young people are closer to change their minds. They are more likely to protect and engage with it.

Attitudes towards Biodiversity
↓
Pre/Post Survey

Mental Health
↓
How do you feel?
↓
Pre/Post Survey

Nº of Target Participants
↓
Survey + Pax list

The scan of A4 papers of the workshop 2 and 3 by the Learning Community of Urban Youth case study. Page 1 – Narrative of change written by the LC members for Night Hike Intervention. Page 2 – Indicators.

Indicators mentioned by the Learning Community:

- **Pre and post survey for attitude change towards biodiversity (preservation)**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Survey data.
Purpose: To understand the change happening within an individual person towards connection with the nature (biophilia hypothesis).
Frequency: Before (one week before) and after the intervention (within a week).
- **Pre and post survey for self-report on mental well-being**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Survey data.
Purpose: To understand the change in mental well-being happening within an individual person.
Frequency: Before (right before the hike) and after the intervention (at the end of the hike).
- **Number of participants with migration background**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Participant list.
Purpose: To monitor attendance of underrepresented group (young people with migrant background) in outdoor activities.
Frequency: After the intervention.

Additionally, qualitative unstructured follow-up 1-on-1 interviews with participants have been mentioned by the Learning Community, but considered too time and capacity-intense, so not written down as notes.

2. Outdoor Movie Night

Attendance
with Pax list
and why did
you come?
↓
Evaluate Personal
Relationships

Attitudes towards
the topic.
Pre - Swipe
↓
Post - Ticket
Ballot Box

Evaluate the
spike in interest
by asking who
has watched
new movies
from the list.

Indicators mentioned by the Learning Community:

- **Number of participants attending the activity**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Participant list.
Purpose: To monitor attendance of.
Frequency: After the intervention.
- **Reason of attendance**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Survey with one question with multiple choice (e.g. Mentimeter)
Purpose: To understand what brought attendance in the first place. One choice could be “because of friends coming along” to test whether the social aspect influences participants engagement and interest in environmental topics, pointing towards social influence as an important factor in measuring change.
Frequency: Before the intervention.
- **Attitudes towards the topic (of the movie)**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Survey.
Purpose: To understand what pre-conception of an individual existed before the movie and what has changed afterwards.
Frequency: Before (quick vote on Mentimeter) and after the intervention (using the ticket for “ballout box” voting).
- **Evaluate the depth of interest on the topic**
Type: Quantitative metric.
Source: Survey.
Purpose: Asking which other movies from the proposed list the participants have watched before, serves both to learn whether they are exposed to the issues, and to stimulate further knowledge acquisition by sharing the possible ways of doing so. And asking re-occurring attendees at each time, in order to predict greater engagement with the topic over time.
Frequency: Before and/or after intervention.

3. Food-Governance Game

*The scan of A4 papers of the workshop 2 and 3 by the Learning Community of Urban Youth case study.
Page 1 – Narrative of change written by the LC members for Biodiversity Food-Governance Game
Intervention. Page 2 – Indicators.*

Indicators mentioned by the Learning Community:

The MLU team has already prepared a quantitative survey and debriefing guidelines (attached as Annex 1). The learning community proposed to enrich the indicators by:

- **Qualitative unstructured follow-up 1-on-1 interviews with participants of the game**
Purpose: Get extra insights into the effects of the game and follow-up activities of young people.
Frequency: Two weeks or a month after the intervention.